

MODERN METHODS FOR ENHANCING THE METHODOLOGICAL
PROFICIENCY OF UPCOMING ECONOMICS TEACHERS

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Abstract. The article talks about the possibilities of the competence approach to improving the methodological competence of future economics teachers. The content of competence, the essence of the concept of scientific research related to the problem of improving the qualifications of the future economics teacher is explained. The development of economic concepts, preparation for independent work and acquisition of skills, competences for working with electronic resources are covered in the manifestation of methodological competence.

Key words: competence, professional competence, methodological competence, specialist, structural structure, target component, didactic features.

Research object and methods

The process of improving the methodological skills of future biology teachers was launched at the Pedagogical Higher Education Institution, and 50 students participated in the Kokan State Pedagogical Institute and the Navoi State Pedagogical Institute.

In the research process, such methods as theoretical (theoretical research of problems, analysis of psychological-pedagogical, scientific-methodical literature); empirical (pedagogical observation, experimental-test work, expert assessment, self-assessment of students, generalization); social methods (questionnaire, question-and-answer, conversation); mathematical-statistical methods (Student's t-criterion) were used.

Research results

In order to implement the idea of integrated use of traditional and information technology tools, to develop ways of more effective assimilation by economics students based on a competency approach, and to check the established research idea and methodology. Designed to integrate traditional teaching and new information technology tools.

In order to successfully implement the educational process according to a certain methodology, it is necessary to have a scientifically based model of this methodology, with the help of which it is possible to describe and analyze the various aspects and elements of the educational process in terms of their mutual

suitability. Determining goals and objectives is undoubtedly the first step in any educational and research activity, including modeling of the educational process and teaching methodology. The target component of the methodology we created is to improve the methodological training of future economics teachers based on the competence approach, as a result of the development of the following set of interrelated goals:

- development of economic concepts;
- training and qualification of independent work;
- composition of competencies for working with electronic resources.

Undoubtedly, the most important goal of the economic teaching methodology is the formation of interrelated knowledge, learning, skills, valuable directions, and intra- and inter-disciplinary interactions.

The formation of students' independence and active attitude to education is of special importance in the educational process, because it plays a special role in the conditions of modernization of higher education and changing the attitude towards education in society. Didactically and methodologically accurate coordination of economic material and computer work in lessons, extracurricular and homework helps to develop independent work skills more effectively, the purpose in this regard is also described. It is also necessary to emphasize the wide opportunities that the described methodology creates for economic education. It is based on the following broad possibilities that a personal computer creates for a student: searching for information on the Internet, electronic textbooks, training programs, working with databases, distance education (not discussed in the scope of our research), etc.

Within this methodology, in addition to the possibilities listed above, all the known possibilities offered by teaching using traditional means are preserved.

The third goal we set is to teach and build skills to work with a computer in the formation of methodological competence. It is necessary to work with a number of programs in cases where they are used in teaching.

In addition to educational and electronic textbooks, text-based operating systems, graphic and HTML editors, multimedia-Proigrivatels, etc. can also be placed.

The variety of means of teaching economics in higher educational institutions is an important condition for effective teaching of the subject. It has unique didactic properties and creates conditions for the existence of different information flows - along different sensory channels, representing different

aspects of the studied object or event in different directions, at different speeds. An important element of the comprehensive application of teaching tools will also be the increase of interest in knowledge on the subject being studied.

The following methodological approaches are determined in connection with the allocated goals: systematic approach; comprehensive approach; person-centered approach; active approach.

A systematic approach is to model, design, describe and implement the methodology (respectively, the educational process) as an open integrated system consisting of interconnected and hierarchically interconnected elements with a fixed structure. is achieved by Also, within the framework of the systemic approach, both the relationships between the elements within the system and the external relationships are defined, created and described. In this approach, it will be possible for students to effectively acquire the necessary knowledge, skills and values, to bring them into a single system, and to achieve the goals and objectives of education [4.5.6].

In pedagogical activity and pedagogical research, a comprehensive approach can be implemented very consistently and applied to various aspects of the educational process, descriptions, and pedagogical experiences. Basically, the definition of a comprehensive approach can be different. In general, a comprehensive approach is understood as the application of a combined, harmonized view of the combined categories or phenomena to achieve a specific goal.

Within the framework of our research, a comprehensive approach is used to describe and use various teaching tools related to the single educational process and the single goal of improving the quality of teaching.

The following functions of a comprehensive approach to the selection of teaching aids can be distinguished:

- maximum consideration of psychophysiological features of students' perception of information;
- creating conditions for more intensive and effective training, when the optimal effect on various analyzers is achieved;
- formation of students' objective ideas about events and processes related to the natural environment;
- description of the set of teaching tools as a whole system with all its components interrelated.

The person-oriented approach determines the need to adapt the pedagogical content, forms, tools and methods of teaching to the individual

capabilities and social, psychological, educational needs of each student. The implementation of a person-oriented approach in the context of the integrated use of traditional teaching tools and IT tools helps to:

- the diversity of educational information transfer methods (text, graphic, tactile, video) allows students with one or another sensory channel of perception to master the content most effectively;
- allows to individualize the speed of learning material;
- allows you to create situations of interest, interest.

The active approach is based on the following rule: the teaching process should be based not only on the simple transfer of information from the source (teacher, teaching tool) to its consumer (student), but also on active independent learning and cognitive activity of students. themselves. Within the framework of our methodology, an active approach was implemented in the lessons with the strengthening of the independent role of students (first of all, personal computers and educational software tools).

As noted above, in the creation of any pedagogical technology or methodology, it lies in the development of a model for achieving the intended goal based on pedagogical approaches. Defining the teaching principles is a very important link in the creation and description of the methodology, which allows connecting general methodological categories with the direct practice of pedagogical activity within the framework of a specific pedagogical technology or methodology.

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